

Making the Invisible Visible: A Global Examination of Careers and Recognition for Imaging Scientists in Core Facilities

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Executive Summary (Abstract)

Imaging facilities underpin a growing share of modern life-science research, yet the career conditions and scholarly recognition of the Imaging Scientists in core facilities who design, deliver, and interpret imaging research remain uneven. This mismatch risks loss of expertise, reduced service quality, and weaker long-term sustainability of shared research capabilities. To provide an evidence base for practical change, we synthesise findings from two complementary international community surveys run by Global BioImaging: a “Top 5” survey on career development and job conditions (>290 responses spanning 43 countries) and an authorship/acknowledgement survey examining how publication credit is assigned for imaging-related contributions of core facility staff (>330 responses spanning 43 countries).

Across both surveys, respondents consistently link limited recognition to constrained career prospects. The career survey highlights recurring bottlenecks around progression routes, job stability and attractiveness, access to professional development, and the day-to-day consequences of being perceived primarily as service providers rather than scientific partners. The authorship/acknowledgement survey documents substantial variability in credit practices across facilities, disciplines, and regions, with many respondents reporting uncertainty about expectations, difficulty initiating credit discussions, and concerns about bias and power dynamics. Taken together, the results suggest a reinforcing cycle: inconsistent credit reduces visibility and leverage for Imaging Scientists in core facilities, which in turn entrenches fragile career pathways and inhibits retention.

We translate these findings into targeted, stakeholder-specific actions. Recommendations focus on defining career paths that match facility roles, aligning evaluation with the full range of facility outputs (including methods, data, software, and training), and ensuring that institutions, funders, publishers, and research teams share responsibility for fair and consistent credit.

Introduction and Background

Advanced imaging has become an indispensable pillar of modern life sciences, underpinning discoveries across biology, medicine, materials science, and translational research. Over the past two decades, imaging workflows have increasingly migrated from individual laboratories into shared imaging core facilities, driven by growing technological complexity, cost, and the need for specialised expertise (1,2,3,4). As a result, Imaging Scientists working in core facilities have become central contributors to experimental design, sample preparation, data acquisition, image analysis, data stewardship, documentation of experimental methods in publications, data visualisation, and user training (5).

In this rapid evolution the professional roles, career pathways, and recognition of Imaging Scientists have not kept pace with their expanding responsibilities. In many research systems, these professionals occupy hybrid positions that combine academic, technical, and service-oriented functions, yet they are still mostly evaluated using frameworks that were designed either for traditional academic research or technical support staff roles. This misalignment creates structural vulnerabilities that affect recruitment, retention, professional development, and the long-term sustainability of imaging infrastructures.

In 2023, the Global BioImaging Working Group on Career Paths for Imaging Scientists published international best-practice recommendations (5,6) that defined the Imaging Scientist role and identified five interlinked, global career-path challenges: (i) lack of recognition of scientific contributions, (ii) mismatch between academic and service-oriented career structures, (iii) funding instability, (iv) limited access to training and professional development, and (v) workforce sustainability and staff retention. That work established a conceptual framework for understanding the Imaging Scientist career ecosystem and highlighted the urgent need for systemic change.

Building on this foundation, the present manuscript provides a deeper analysis of global trends of the specific Top 5 Career Path Challenges that Imaging Scientists face, explored through a large-scale international survey, as well as a more in-depth look at authorship and acknowledgement practices, examined through a complementary survey focused on recognition of core facility staff in scientific publications.

These two components are tightly interconnected. Recognition through authorship and acknowledgement is not merely symbolic; it directly influences how Imaging Scientists are evaluated, promoted, and resourced within institutions (7,8). Although publication metrics alone are insufficient to capture the full impact of facility-based work, they remain a dominant currency in academic evaluation and funding systems. Inconsistent or absent recognition therefore exacerbates many of the career path challenges previously identified, reinforcing misalignment between contribution and recognition.

To address these issues, the Global BioImaging (GBI) Working Group adopted a community-driven approach, deploying two coordinated surveys across the GBI community between 2023 and 2025. The first survey focused on identifying and contextualising the Top 5 Career Path Challenges across regions, institutional settings, and stakeholder groups. The second survey examined global practices and perceptions related to authorship and acknowledgement of Imaging Scientists and imaging facilities. Through their international nature and broad response rate, the surveys also contain valuable general data about imaging core facilities around the world, which is why the full survey datasets are shared openly (9) in an anonymised fashion alongside this publication for further analysis by interested community members, complementing also the extensive data in the International microscopy core facility benchmarking survey (10).

By integrating diverse global perspectives on these issues, we aim to (i) quantify and contextualise the most pressing career challenges faced by Imaging Scientists worldwide, (ii) provide empirical evidence on how current authorship and acknowledgement practices contribute to these challenges in different regional contexts, and (iii) identify actionable pathways for Imaging Scientists, institutions, funders,

publishers, and research communities to strengthen recognition, career development, and the long-term resilience of imaging core facilities.

Highlight box 1: Recommendations for stakeholders - what to change and who can change it

Hosting institutions

- Define career paths that match hybrid facility roles (including service, research, innovation, training, and more).
- Recognize the entire scope of facility-enabled outputs for their staff evaluation (including methods, technology, workflows, and software development, data FAIRification, user training, collaboration building, and innovation management).
- Embed recognition expectations in internal policies (e.g., contribution statements, facility acknowledgement guidance).
- Provide protected time for staff development and community leadership.

Funders

- Ask applicants to include a “recognition and contribution plan” for facility, technical, and support staff (authorship, acknowledgements, data stewardship).
- Allow eligible costs for facility scientist time beyond instrument access (experimental design, analysis, training, FAIR data work).
- Use evaluation criteria that reward shared capability building, not only PI-led publications.
- Support sustainability mechanisms and facility-led grants (multi-year operational funding; staff retention and training lines).

Publishers

- Require transparent contribution statements that make facility expertise visible (including experimental design, image acquisition, analysis, data curation).
- Encourage standardized facility acknowledgements (including use of PIDs and CRediT) and consistent citation of methods/tools.
- Provide clear editorial guidance on when specialist facility contributions warrant authorship versus acknowledgement.
- Promote metadata practices that improve discoverability of facility contributions.

Principal investigators and research teams

- Discuss credit early - before data collection - and revisit at milestones (design, analysis, manuscript drafting).
- Use facility-provided acknowledgement statements, follow authorship guidelines, and document contributions as they occur.
- Include Imaging Scientists when their expertise shapes study design, interpretation, or analysis; acknowledge facilities and individual staff members consistently otherwise.
- Avoid “payment substitutes credit”: paying for access does not replace scholarly recognition.

Facility leadership and existing Networks (including Global BioImaging partners)

- Co-develop community guidelines and training for authorship/acknowledgement conversations, and tools and best practises contribution tracking.
- Track recognition metrics over time (authorship/acknowledgement rates; satisfaction; guideline uptake) to benchmark progress.
- Use aggregated evidence to advocate for policy change at institutional and national levels.

Methodology

This manuscript is based on data generated through two complementary, international, community-driven surveys developed and disseminated by the Global BioImaging (GBI) Working Group on Career Paths for Imaging Scientists¹. The Working Group brings together imaging core facility professionals, researchers, and infrastructure representatives from all GBI partner communities, enabling broad geographical and institutional reach.

The **Top 5 Career Path Challenges** survey was deployed between 2023 and December 2024, with continued targeted dissemination into mid-2025 to address regional underrepresentation identified during preliminary analyses. The **Authorship and Acknowledgement** survey has been conducted since January 2025. Data for the analysis presented here was collected until December 2025, but the survey remains open for further contributions from the community, which will inform further analysis and work on the topic.

Questions in both surveys combined structured multiple-choice items with open-text responses to enable both quantitative analysis and qualitative insight into systemic challenges affecting Imaging Scientists and core facilities worldwide. The full set of questions from both surveys is available in Supplemental Document 1.

Both surveys were directed at Imaging Scientists and core facility staff, explicitly including individuals performing core facility equivalent roles in institutions without formalised core facilities. Contributors to the surveys also included members from the broader Imaging Scientist universe as described in our previous publication (5). Surveys were piloted within the working group (data not included) and refined based on that initial feedback to ensure clarity of questions in different facility contexts and that sufficient background information was collected for analysis. Figure 1(A) below was also included in the Top 5 survey at a later date to more accurately understand the respondent demographics as the study evolved - not all respondents have answered all questions.

Both surveys were disseminated centrally through the GBI network and the GBI partner communities - both virtually and at the GBI Exchange of Experience conferences and all the partner community meetings. Further distribution took place via international, national, and regional bioimaging community events, community channels online, individual networks, social media, and other partner communities, ensuring representation across continents, facility types, and imaging modalities. Responses were collected in a GDPR-compliant manner with respondents informed about the potential use of anonymised data in publications. Responses were anonymised prior to analysis. Quantitative data were analysed descriptively to identify global patterns and regional trends, while qualitative responses were thematically coded to contextualise and interpret the survey findings. Graphs were constructed in either Biorender or Microsoft Excel.

¹ <https://globalbioimaging.org/working-groups/career-paths>

As with all self-reporting surveys, several limitations must be acknowledged in the interpretation of this data. Responses reflect individual experiences and perceptions, which are influenced by local institutional culture, career stage, and personal context, introducing potential perception bias. Institutional structures and terminology vary substantially across countries, which may affect how questions were interpreted. In addition, recognition practices often involve informal or private decision-making processes, meaning that some respondents may not have full visibility of institutional policies or publication-related discussions. Despite these limitations, the consistency of key themes across regions, facility types, and stakeholder groups suggests that the findings capture robust, systemic patterns. Collectively, the surveys represent the most comprehensive global dataset to date on career challenges and recognition practices affecting Imaging Scientists predominantly working in core facilities in life sciences.

Results

Top 5 Challenges

More than 290 responses from 43 countries were evaluated to gain a deeper understanding of the career path challenges faced by Imaging Scientists in various countries and continents. The data are presented as overall key challenges faced globally, along with a breakdown of continent-specific challenges and those within the Imaging Scientist Venn Diagram.

A

1	Dedicated Core Staff	Dedicated 100% to enabling access and providing support to imaging technologies (Facility operations, training, service, maintenance, and administration) EM/LM/HCS/Bioimaging/Image Analysis.
2	Core Staff with split remit	Shared role (may include staff working in another core facility other than imaging core (e.g. Image Analysis/Flow Cytometry/Histology/Sequencing/Mass Spec/Biomedical (Preclinical)/Medical/In Vivo imaging/Animal Facility/Medical Imaging) .
3	Not Core facility affiliated Imaging Scientists	(Academic) Staff engaged in the field of imaging technologies and applications, whether or not formally affiliated with a core facility, but who significantly contribute to core facility operations or perform equivalent core facility roles in institutions that lack dedicated core facilities.
4	Principal Researchers and Investigators	PIs with influence and/or responsibility for oversight, steering groups/committees. This may include roles in budget allocation, future-proofing, strategy, sustainability and staffing matters.
5	Industry-related	Industry funded positions or seconded staff working within core facilities.
6	Technology developers	In academia or industry, the people who are developing new imaging solutions.
7	Industry exclusive	Applications specialists, engineers and sales delegates

B

Breakdown of respondents per group from Venn Diagram

C

(Combination of) Group selections from Venn Diagram

Figure 1: A. The varied roles of Imaging Scientists. This figure is modified from (5) Wright et al., 2024 (DOI: 10.1111/jmi.13307). Survey data encompasses contributions from all of the groups listed 1-7 above but primarily focuses on groups 1-5. B, C. Survey respondents per group and the group combinations selected from the Venn Diagram (N=290). Groups as per A. This data sheds light onto the role structure breakdown. Not all respondents to the survey provided this information as this question was added to the survey after its initial deployment.

Over 33% of respondents occupy hybrid or cross-group roles. This suggests that current single-track career frameworks fail to reflect the structurally blended nature of modern research and core-facility work. It also highlights that hybrid roles, particularly those intersecting between Group 1 (Imaging core facility) and Group 4 (PIs), are a structural **feature of modern research infrastructures** rather than an exception, **particularly in facility leadership** (11). The high frequency of: Group 1 (Imaging core facilities) + Group 2 (non-imaging CFs), Group 1 + Group 3 (Researchers), Group(s) + Group 4 combinations in the selections indicate that **blended academic, technical, leadership, and service identities are the norm, not edge cases**. Group 4, at over one quarter of all responses, functions as a core identity group that cuts across Groups 1–3. This would **strongly support arguments for new diversified career frameworks and recognition models**. The data empirically supports the argument that current career tracks and

single-label role classifications, along with binary “academic vs support” models, do not reflect how people actually work.

The Top5 career path challenges dataset reveals a consistent **frustration with structural undervaluation and resource limitations**, balanced by a forward-looking recognition of Imaging Scientists’ evolving roles in data, AI, and translational research. The responses collectively point toward a need for **institutional reform, structured career frameworks, and sustainable investment** in both people and infrastructure.

Figure2: Proportional Representation from Respondents to the Top5 Survey. Location of contributors indicated on the map (not colour coded to donut chart) with detailed percentage breakdown per continent/geopolitical grouping. Please refer to Supplemental Document 2 for countries included in each geographical subdivision.

When asked about what actions should be taken to improve the current situation, 62% responded the implementation of clear career paths for Imaging Scientists, 52% raising awareness and visibility on the scientific value and impact Imaging Scientists have, 42% sustainable funding to attract and retain staff, and 40% professional training and development activities for Imaging Scientists.

Figure 3: Frequency of workforce priorities identified for Imaging Scientists across multi-selection survey responses. Respondents (n=290) were asked to prioritise two of the challenges based on urgency and need for change. Reform of the Imaging Scientist career pathway is the most frequently cited issue (210 mentions), followed by addressing recognition of value and impact (160 mentions).

Global Comparative Analysis of Challenges Faced by Imaging Core Facility Scientists

A comparative analysis across seven world regions - Europe, Africa, India, Asia, North America (US, Canada and Mexico), Central and South America, and Oceania (Australia & New Zealand) - reveals a complex but coherent global landscape of structural challenges affecting Imaging Scientists and core facility personnel (see Table 1).

Data analysed as part of the regional study has assisted with identifying the main challenges in different parts of the world. The in-depth analysis of the groups represented on the Venn Diagram illuminates how the challenges each group experiences cascade through the ecosystem and who experiences each consequence. Specific highlights from those participants who selected Group 1 are included in the sections below. Of particular concern, the data indicates that some in the field experience “burnout” due to chronic understaffing and operational bottlenecks. Together, these perspectives demonstrate that imaging science requires coordinated global action that is both **universal in recognizing shared systemic barriers** and **locally adaptable in addressing region-specific resource contexts, institutional maturity levels, and the needs of Imaging Scientists working in different role contexts**.

Comparative Analysis: Regional and Stakeholder Perspectives

Career progression emerges as the single most universal challenge, identified as critical across all regions and stakeholder groups (50% of responses from participants who identified as Group 1

primarily), yet this challenge is experienced distinctly: *high-income regions report career path misalignment with academic promotion systems*, while *low-income regions describe an absence of formalized career frameworks entirely*. Facility staff (Groups 1-3) experience this as blocked advancement and HR misclassification, while principal investigators (Group 4) observe it through high turnover and talent loss to industry. Representative quotes from Group 1 reflecting on this challenge include: "Core facility roles don't fit traditional academic or technical job ladders. This leads to unclear promotion paths", "Flat hierarchies leave no room for career progression within a facility. Therefore ambitious staff must leave to progress", and "No dedicated career track as a core facility staff". The prevalence and dominance of short-term contracts (between 1-3 years) were mentioned frequently and clearly contradict the need for deep expertise and institutional memory. The resulting feeling of instability in the position and undervaluation leads to talent loss. Heavy workloads due to staff shortages are explicitly cited as a barrier to skill upgrading by Imaging facility staff. Participants cite being too busy to train/develop skills, but conversely needing these advanced skills to remain competitive in the field, be it locally, nationally or internationally. What is clear from the data is that this is not just about participants wanting promotion, it is about the complete absence of clear pathways for skill development and growth in roles that does not fit existing academic or technical frameworks.

Funding instability similarly *affects all regions and roles* but operates through different mechanisms: *low-income regions face absolute resource scarcity that prevents basic infrastructure development*, whereas *high-income regions struggle with strategic challenges such as cost-recovery models and insufficient long-term planning*. 23% of Group 1 participants highlighted this as their top challenge and explicitly mentioned "expectation to cover all operational costs, including running costs, equipment maintenance and salary" and "Lack of financial support to acquire new equipment" as part of their responses in this category. The stakeholder analysis demonstrates how these funding constraints cascade: *facility staff cannot replace aging equipment, principal investigators face research delays, and industry partners find institutional markets unreceptive to innovation*.

Recognition deficits, prominently reported in *high-income regions* but less emphasized in Africa where foundational barriers dominate, illustrate how cultural undervaluation translates into structural consequences. Groups 1-3 report personal undervaluation and insufficient authorship credit, while Groups 5-7 observe that lack of recognition directly impedes funding decisions and technology adoption.

Training gaps are universally reported but reflect vastly different barriers: *low-income regions* lack accessible programs on even foundational techniques and face geographic and language constraints, while *high-income regions* require more specialized training in advanced modalities. Across all contexts, facility staff report insufficient time for professional development, principal investigators note reduced data quality from inadequately trained users, and industry identifies a widening scientific literacy gap. Further to this, data from Group 1 indicates that there are often language barriers as most international training courses are run in English only and the perpetuation of a two-tier system continues to exist: those with access to training vs. those without. Participants note there tend to be few local opportunities, and international courses are held mostly in the global north, many of which are over-

subscribed, and geopolitical uncertainty has made attaining visas to travel to these courses more difficult in recent years for some.

Critically, the analysis of both datasets converge on the finding that **these challenges are deeply interconnected** (see Table 2): *lack of recognition is perceived to constrain investment, unstable funding restricts staffing and training, underdeveloped career pathways weaken retention, and insufficient training undermines scientific output.*

While the survey data are self-reported and do not establish causal relationships, the consistency of observed patterns across regions, facility types, and stakeholder groups strongly suggests the presence of underlying structural interdependencies within the global imaging ecosystem - highlighting the importance of coordinated, international approaches such as those driven by Global BioImaging in identifying systemic challenges that may not be visible individually at local or national scales.

Solutions must therefore operate at the systems level:

1. Establishing regional - or ideally global - career frameworks with national flexibility
2. Differentiating funding strategies by economic context while addressing cascade effects,
3. Building recognition culture that demonstrates operational return on investment, and
4. Creating geographically accessible training with protected time across all professional roles

Figure 4: Recommendations for the required steps and interdependencies on the establishment of the Imaging Scientist Career Path

The health of the imaging ecosystem depends not on optimizing individual components but on the alignment and mutual support of all regions and stakeholder groups simultaneously.

Region	Primary Challenge	Secondary Challenges	Insights
Europe	Recognition	Career Path Mismatch; Funding	Strong cultural undervaluation; structural barriers despite mature infrastructure.
North America (US, Canada, Mexico)	Recognition	Career Path Mismatch; Talent	Similar to Europe: under-recognition of imaging scientists, staff leaving for industry.
Central & South America	Funding Instability	Recognition; Career Path Mismatch	Severe systemic underinvestment; unstable infrastructure; undervaluation also strong.
Africa	Funding Instability	Training Deficits; Talent Shortages	Most severe funding constraints globally; foundational capacity-building needed.
India	Training Deficits	Recognition; Talent	Rapidly expanding research ecosystem but limited national training infrastructure.
SEA & Japan	Funding Instability	Recognition; Career Path Mismatch	Mixed-income region: uneven infrastructure, strong recognition concerns.
Oceania	Career Path Mismatch	Recognition; Funding; Talent	Highest global prevalence of mismatch; structural HR misalignment dominates.

Table 1 - Regional breakdown of the top listed challenges.

Constraint	Systemic Impact
Career Instability	Undermines retention, weakens facility continuity, erosion of institutional memory
Underfunding	Limits scientific capability, delayed technology adoption, workforce instability
Insufficient Recognition	Shapes funding decisions, career structures, institutional priorities
Training Limitations	Impede scientific reproducibility, reduce facility efficiency, weaken institutional competitiveness
Excessive Workload	Compromised data quality, constrained innovation and reduced community training capacity
Capital Underinvestment	Stagnant imaging capability, plateauing scientific output, less competitive workforce and research environment
<p>The imaging ecosystem is interconnected. Improvement requires a systems-level approach:</p> <p>Funding → Staffing → Recognition → Training → Research outputs → Innovation → Investment</p>	

Table 2: Stability in the above listed factors are a necessity for any high-performing research and imaging environment. Underfunding at any point in the ecosystem reverberates across all other points.

Across all respondent groups, the findings highlight the urgent need for a coherent, sustainable strategy for imaging science that recognises Imaging Scientists as **intellectual contributors**, invests in modern infrastructure, establishes transparent career pathways, stabilises funding, and provides structured training across roles. This has been reported in the literature over the past decade as core facilities have developed and evolved (12).

These patterns paint a consistent picture across global facilities:

Need for clearer career pathways - Core facility imaging staff globally identify career progression as their overwhelming top challenge. The data reveals a workforce caught between institutional expectations for expertise and sustainability, and systematic barriers to professional development, stability, and recognition. There is a **clear need for structural career frameworks** that recognize the hybrid academic/technical expertise of Imaging Scientists (for more details see 5 (Annex B)). Academic promotions rarely extend to facility-based experts, and in the event they are available, the academic merit criteria often do not adequately recognise the distinct responsibilities and performance of an Imaging Scientist, compared to a traditional academic role, leading to an **under-evaluation of the Imaging Scientists**.

Need for recognition and suitable staff evaluation - A persistent challenge for Imaging Scientists is the lack of a **formal institutional career ladder** for professionals whose roles uniquely **blend academic, technical, and service-oriented expertise**. In many research institutions, there is no clearly defined pathway for progression, from entry-level assistant roles to intermediate technical and scientific positions, and ultimately to leadership roles such as core facility manager or senior imaging specialist. Establishing structured positions with transparent competencies and promotion criteria is essential not only for professional recognition but also for sustaining high-quality imaging support within research ecosystems. This gap highlights the need for a global conversation: *we must collectively advocate for research institutions worldwide to formally acknowledge and develop career frameworks that reflect the complexity and value of Imaging Scientists' contributions*.

Need for sustainability of positions - In addition, the need for **sustainable and reliable funding**, both for operations and staff (recruitment and retention), remains a pressing concern. There is often a lack of long-term strategic institutional support for core facility infrastructure, which impacts the stability and attractiveness of the available positions. Cost recovery mechanisms, whilst key to recouping day-to-day expenses like basic laboratory consumable, maintenance costs, and service contracts, are generally not sufficient to ensure growth and development of the facility, and are dependent on the overall success of grant income and the local ecosystem and fluctuate year-on-year.

Need for professional development and training activities - Following from the lack of clear career paths and job descriptions, there is a consequent lack of accessible tailored professional development activities. **Training pathways for Imaging Scientists are underserved**, and existing opportunities to upskill or specialise are perceived as inaccessible or inconsistent. The inaccessibility arises from a range of different factors. In many cases Imaging Scientists do not have the opportunity to take advantage of existing training opportunities due to financial and/or time allocation constraints, especially in core facilities with small teams. Training opportunities are furthermore not equally distributed across career stages. Overall, this demonstrates the lack of recognition of the importance of systematic skills development and the resulting lack of structured support for the technical and professional development of Imaging Scientists.

Authorship and Acknowledgement practices regarding Imaging Scientist Contributions

Across the Top 5 Career Path Challenges, recognition emerges as a foundational prerequisite for sustainable career development of Imaging Scientists. While a broad set of appropriate metrics beyond publications is needed to capture the full scope of core facility contributions, the primary mission of imaging facilities remains the support of excellent research, and scientific publications are the principal means by which this research is communicated - making fair recognition of Imaging Scientists' contributions in authorship and acknowledgement an essential component of the research process.

Imaging Scientists contribute substantially to research design, data acquisition, analysis, and interpretation, and facility expertise is often recognised by the researchers directly involved in experiments. However, authorship and acknowledgement decisions are typically made later in the publication process and by individuals who may be less aware of the scope of facility contributions. As a result, Imaging Scientists and core facilities are frequently omitted from authorship lists, and acknowledgements are given inconsistently (these are also not indexed or searchable with bibliometric software).

The following section presents results from an international survey examining how authorship and acknowledgement practices for Imaging Scientists are currently applied across regions, facility types, and institutional contexts, and how these practices influence professional recognition and career development.

Global Landscape mapping

To date, the Global BioImaging Authorship & Acknowledgement Survey has collected more than 330 responses from Imaging Scientists and core facility personnel across all GBI partner communities, representing a diverse range of institutions, imaging facility types, and geographical contexts (Figure 6 A and B). Respondents included staff from Electron Microscopy, Light Microscopy, Preclinical and Clinical Imaging, and Image Analysis facilities (Figure 6D), as well as individuals providing core facility-equivalent support in settings without formalised core facilities (Figure 6C). Although efforts were made to reach Imaging Scientists from all geographic regions and all Global BioImaging communities are included in the analysis below, response rates are quite diverse across the world, with particularly high response rates in Europe and Australia, and lower rates in geographic areas where core facilities are not yet institutionally well-established, such as South America, Africa and South East Asia.

Figure 5 - Survey respondent characterisation. A) Regional breakdown of respondents to the survey on Authorship and Acknowledgement of Imaging Scientists in core facilities. B) World map with all countries of respondents to the survey highlighted (not colour coded to donut chart). C) Distribution of survey respondents between those working in a core facility and those fulfilling core facility equivalent roles in institutions without formalised CFs. D) Breakdown of the service areas of the CF represented by the respondents.

1. Global Patterns in Recognition

Across the global dataset, the survey revealed a diverse landscape of authorship and acknowledgement practices among imaging core facilities, with substantial variation by technology, facility size, and region. When asked about their overall experiences with authorship, respondents consistently described a **mixed situation** (Figure 6): most indicated that core facility staff were included as co-authors in only around half of the relevant publications, and often less (Figure 6C). First or last authorships were extremely rare, which is expected given the role that core facility staff normally play in publications. But middle authorship also occurred only sporadically, which represents a critical sign for underrepresentation of Imaging Scientists in authorship lists. Acknowledgements were far more frequent, with “sometimes” and “often” being the most common reporting categories across all respondents. Satisfaction with recognition remained generally low to moderate (Figure 6B), reflecting persistent frustration that meaningful intellectual and technical contributions are not routinely translated into formal professional credit.

Figure 6 - Authorship rates and satisfaction (n=330). A) Response rates on a scale from 1 (Never) to 10 (Always) assessing how frequently CF team members are given authorships of publications for their contributions to these publications, B) Response rates on a scale from 1 (Not satisfied) to 10 (Very satisfied) for individual satisfaction with the current recognition of core facility Imaging Scientists in authorship. C) Frequency of core facility team members acknowledged in publications in the different forms.

2. Facility and Region-Specific Differences

Clear patterns emerged when comparing facilities by technological focus (Figure 7). **Respondents from electron microscopy (EM) facilities reported higher levels of recognition.** They described being acknowledged more consistently, receiving co-authorship more frequently, and expressing greater satisfaction with their recognition overall. Many EM facility respondents also felt more empowered to advocate for appropriate credit, both for themselves and for their colleagues.

In contrast, respondents from **light-microscopy-only (LM) facilities**, and those combining LM with **(pre)clinical imaging, reported significantly lower levels of both co-authorship and acknowledgement.** While they were often acknowledged, authorship remained infrequent, and a considerable proportion of respondents indicated very low satisfaction with their recognition. Facilities that offered both LM and EM reported more balanced results, with values falling between the two extremes. Other facility types were represented by too few responses to allow meaningful analysis.

These differences in authorship and acknowledgement levels between EM facilities and other imaging facilities may be due to differences in the way EM facility staff are involved in user projects. Although this is not universal, in many EM facilities, staff are more centrally involved in both sample preparation

and image acquisition, compared to LM facilities, where oftentimes users are trained for self-sufficient use of microscopes and therefore authorship is rarer. In all facility types, Imaging Scientists provide key contributions, but different levels of involvement and perhaps varying perceptions of technical complexities of different methods may impact the recognition levels.

Figure 7: Rate of A) Co-authorship and b) Acknowledgement compared across different facility types from those offering only Electron Microscopy (EM), only Light Microscopy (LM), combinations of Light Microscopy and preclinical imaging techniques (LM+preclinical), and combination of Light and Electron Microscopy (LM+EM) (n=319). Response rates from other facility groups were too small for reliable analysis.

Facility size also shaped recognition practices and perceptions. Very **small facilities**, those staffed by only one or two individuals, reported broadly similar authorship and acknowledgement frequencies to other facilities, but consistently lower satisfaction. Respondents in such settings emphasised in their free text responses that recognition encompasses more than authorship alone; institutional support, career development opportunities, and clarity of expectations also play a critical role, and these often lag behind in very small facilities. These respondents were also more likely to work in institutions without any formal authorship or acknowledgement guidelines.

Large facilities, with more than ten staff members, described similar authorship patterns but reported more frequent acknowledgements and generally higher satisfaction with recognition. Approximately 70% of respondents in this group indicated that their institution had formal guidelines in place, although nearly one-third of these felt that the guidelines were insufficiently clear or well-developed. **Medium-sized facilities** (five to ten staff members) displayed a more complex pattern: authorship and acknowledgement practices resembled those of larger facilities, but personal satisfaction was split into two nearly equal groups, one cluster of respondents reporting fairly high satisfaction, and another reporting very low satisfaction. Institutional support was also less consistent in this group, with only about 55% confirming the existence of official guidelines.

Geographical patterns added further complexity. Respondents from Japan reported moderate institutional support but comparatively high levels of co-authorship and acknowledgement, coupled with higher personal satisfaction than the global average. In contrast, responses from Southeast Asia and Africa indicated predominantly medium levels of acknowledgement, low levels of authorship, and predominantly mid to low satisfaction, though additional responses may refine this interpretation as the survey continues. Respondents from India described almost no access to institutional authorship guidelines, extremely low levels of authorship, moderate levels of acknowledgement, and resultantly low personal satisfaction.

Respondents from Central and South American countries showed a distinct pattern: institutional guidelines were scarce, yet levels of co-authorship were moderate, acknowledgements comparatively high, and satisfaction extremely heterogeneous - roughly half of respondents described moderate satisfaction, while the remainder reported very low satisfaction. Responses from Australia were particularly striking, given the strength of national imaging networks: fewer than half of facilities reported institutional guidelines, and 26% indicated that existing guidance lacked clarity. At the same time, an individual check of 20 Australian universities, including all G8 institutions - performed by an Australian member of the GBI working group - showed that all have institutional guidelines which specifically include non-standard data collection and analysis of research data as sufficient to warrant

authorship (13). Therefore these responses likely reflect a lack of awareness and lack of promotion of existing guidelines. Co-authorship was generally described as occurring “sometimes,” acknowledgements were frequent, and satisfaction was surprisingly low.

European respondents reported the highest levels of institutional guidance (61%), moderate co-authorship rates, and strong acknowledgement practices. Indeed, several European facilities reported being “always” acknowledged. Correspondingly, European respondents expressed relatively high satisfaction with recognition.

In North America, fewer than half of respondents had institutional guidelines, and 31% of those described their guidelines as poorly developed. Co-authorship levels were lower, acknowledgements moderate, and personal satisfaction distinctly bimodal: one large cluster of respondents expressed relatively high satisfaction, while another indicated very low satisfaction. These regional trends should be contextualised by differences in facility-type representation in the dataset - Europe and Australia, for example, had strong participation from EM facilities which are associated with higher acknowledgement rates.

3. Institutional Frameworks and Barriers

Institutional frameworks have the power to impact recognition practices significantly. However, as outlined above, the presence of institutional guidelines varies widely - with them being fairly widespread in some regions, while almost absent in others. However, even in settings with existing official policies, there are challenges around Imaging Scientists' and researchers' awareness of these, their clarity and applicability to core facility contributions, and core facility staffs ability to enforce existing rules without fear of repercussions. In some settings, facility staff are explicitly excluded from authorship considerations by local policies or institutional culture, while in others, expectations are unclear or inconsistently applied.

Proactive initiatives to improve recognition were described as being **driven predominantly by core facilities themselves**, with 55% of respondents identifying the facility as the main source of advocacy for authorship and acknowledgement. Departments played only a limited role (11%), and other institutional or community initiatives accounted for a mere 7%. Survey respondents identified several major barriers to appropriate recognition: lack of awareness among researchers, institutional culture resistant to change, the absence of clear policies, and insufficient advocacy mechanisms. Each of these was selected by approximately 20–25% of respondents, reflecting the distributed, multi-factorial nature of the problem.

4. Equity, Bias, and Advocacy

The survey also indicated concerning bias in recognition practices. 13% of female core facility staff reported experiencing gender bias directly, and an additional 46% selected “not sure”, suggesting that almost 60% of women perceived some likelihood or potential of bias. In contrast, only 4% of male respondents reported gender bias, with 23% unsure. Respondents also noted differences in recognition

between staff members with and without PhDs (with 21% reporting bias and 24% uncertain), as well as patterns linked to seniority, where 15% perceived bias and an additional 15% were unsure. These patterns, particularly regarding the acknowledgement of facility staff with and without PhDs, seem to be robust as they are similar independent of respondents seniority or facility role.

Patterns of self-advocacy also emerged. Approximately two-thirds of respondents reported advocating for themselves and their colleagues either regularly or occasionally (Figure 8A). This behaviour appeared largely independent of facility size, although regional variation existed: self-advocacy was somewhat more common in Europe and lower in Japan, with other regions showing no particularly distinct trends. The one-third of respondents who did not advocate often cited a belief that advocacy would be ineffective, reluctance to initiate conflict, or fear of retaliation from senior researchers. Forty-three percent reported having experienced conflicts regarding recognition in publications (Figure 8B), which should also be seen in context with survey data on conflict management in core facilities published in this same issue (14). Respondents also noted insufficient leadership support, both within facilities and at higher institutional levels, as a major deterrent to advocacy.

Systemic factors outside of the control of both the researchers using the facilities and the Imaging Scientists themselves further contributed to the problem: many Imaging Scientists reported in the survey that they simply learned about publications too late to engage in discussions on authorship, and in many facilities, the individuals interacting with users are more junior than those making authorship decisions, creating power imbalances that hinder self-advocacy. At the same time, survey respondents highlight that their facility users often fully recognise the importance of the facility contributions but that these are often more junior researchers, while the PIs who make final authorship decisions on manuscripts rarely use the facilities themselves and therefore have less view of the core facility contributions.

The wide-spread perception that payment for facility services negates the need for authorship recognition also influences facility staff psychologically, making some facility staff themselves undervalue their own contribution. Perspectives on this opinion often shift when people are made aware that all contributors to research are paid for their work. Some respondents also noted a conceptual disconnect: because publications are not part of their performance evaluation or personal motivation, they feel less compelled to advocate despite recognising the broader professional implications.

Figure 8: A) Frequency at which core facility staff report advocating for themselves or their colleagues when it comes to recognition in both authorships and acknowledgements. B) Percentage of staff reporting having experienced conflict around authorship or acknowledgement discussions.

5. Impacts on Careers and Facility Sustainability

Respondents linked inadequate recognition to several key consequences: impaired job evaluation, reduced promotion and career advancement opportunities, and diminished ability to secure funding. In contrast, impacts on attracting new users or staff were perceived as relatively minor, suggesting that the consequences of insufficient acknowledgement are primarily internal, affecting careers, retention, and institutional visibility, rather than external.

Figure 9: Circular Dependencies - Changes in any of the above circles can cause a knock on effect on the others.

The survey did not address the external impact of lack of acknowledgement from a research or university ecosystem standpoint, where such a lack of long standing co-authorships between PIs and imaging facility staff may impact researchers ability to convincingly propose complex and ambitious imaging workflows in their grants, leading to a potential loss of funding for the institution.

Taken together, the survey findings demonstrate that inadequate recognition is **not a localised issue but a global, structural problem that affects Imaging Scientists across facility types, institutions, and continents**. Several themes emerge clearly. First, cultural and institutional expectations strongly shape recognition practices: facilities with clear policies or established cultures of collaboration report higher satisfaction and more equitable authorship outcomes. Second, lack of awareness among researchers, particularly regarding the intellectual contributions of core facility staff, remains a fundamental barrier. Survey respondents raised the challenge that some scientists and institutional leaders still perceive Imaging Scientists in core facilities as technicians who take pictures, rather than as experts with specialized and unique expertise who make valuable contributions in their field that accelerate scientific discovery and innovation. Third, the burden of securing appropriate recognition rests disproportionately on individual Imaging Scientists, who must advocate for authorship despite often lacking institutional support or even support from the leadership within their own facilities. This **reliance on individual advocacy is neither sustainable nor equitable, and underscores the need for systemic interventions**. The implementation of project onboarding processes clearly describing the role of core facility staff, aligning contribution expectations, intellectual property acknowledgments and clear institutional recommendations or guidelines could remove inequities and harmonize the international landscape.

Importantly, the findings highlight that **improved recognition is not only a matter of fairness**. Authorship and acknowledgement data serve as **critical evidence for evaluating facility impact, securing institutional resources, and demonstrating return on investment to funders (Figure 9) (8)**. Strengthening recognition practices therefore enhances both career progression for individuals and institutional sustainability for imaging facilities.

The acknowledgement of core facilities goes beyond simple courtesy. Identifying the origin of data (and associated metadata) is essential to ensuring data FAIRness, and it should be accepted that central facilities are major generators of data in modern life sciences research (2). By involving facility staff in the publication process, either through authorship or appropriate acknowledgement, richer information about the sample preparation and acquisition, can be added, cross-checked and validated by the larger research team. Strengthening acknowledgement practices also improves future data governance and provenance, increases the metadata quality and the integrity and reproducibility of the research.

These implications directly reinforce the need for clear policies, visible guidelines, appropriate mechanisms for crediting facility contributions, and a shift toward shared credit and responsibility between researchers, facility managers, and institutional leadership. Although this comprehensive study, the first of its kind worldwide, specifically addresses the case of Imaging Scientists working in imaging facilities, most of the reflections and recommendations match with published data from initiatives focussing regionally or on core facility scientists generally (15,16, 17).

Recommendations and Community-Driven Solutions

The survey findings highlight that improving recognition practices requires action at multiple levels, but they also demonstrate that effective, community-driven solutions already exist. Across regions, Imaging Scientists and core facility communities, including non-imaging specific communities such as CTLS² and ABRF³, have begun to develop practical tools and initiatives that translate policy principles into everyday practice. These efforts provide concrete examples that can be adapted, scaled, and adopted by other institutions and national communities.

One such example is the continued development and dissemination of the *Imaging Facility Guidelines for Acknowledgement*, originally developed by the Royal Microscopical Society⁴ and BioImagingUK. Recognising the need for global accessibility, the Global BioImaging Working Group has developed translations of these guidelines into so far 13 languages and the development of accompanying guidance on their practical use within facilities. These materials aim to facilitate early and transparent discussions about authorship and acknowledgement, support consistent recognition practices, and lower barriers for facility staff to advocate for the application of existing guidelines in day-to-day interactions with users. The initial campaign saw over 400 downloads across more than 40 countries (Figure 10) with the most downloaded editions being English, Portuguese, Spanish, Japanese, Chinese, Bahasa Malaysia, and French, reflecting strong global uptake and relevance⁵. Their broad international interest underscores the **value of shared, community-owned tools for addressing recognition challenges**.

Figure 10: Imaging Facility Guidelines for Acknowledgement - downloads and distribution with detailed percentage breakdown per continent/geopolitical grouping (not colour coded to donut chart). Please refer to Supplemental Document 2 for countries included in each geographical subdivision.

² <https://ctls-org.eu/>

³ <https://abrf.org/>

⁴ <https://www.rms.org.uk/library/core-facilities-publication-policy.html>

⁵ <https://globalbioimaging.org/documents/imaging-facility-guidelines>

Beyond imaging-specific initiatives, broader efforts across the research ecosystem further demonstrate that increased visibility and recognition of technical expertise is achievable. In the United Kingdom, the *Times Higher Education Technician of the Year Award*, and the inclusion of facilities in the national *Research Excellence Framework* driven by the *Hidden REF* initiative⁶, all elevate the visibility of technical expertise across a wide range of research expertise. The *Technical Specialists Network (TSN)*⁷ and the *Institute for Technical Skills and Strategy (ITSS)*⁸ further strengthen career development opportunities for technical staff through dedicated funding and training, building on initial advocacy work by the Technician Commitment initiative⁹, which is now also starting to find adoptions beyond the UK where it originated.

Although these initiatives are often regionally rooted, they provide transferable models and reinforce the message that Imaging Scientists are part of a wider community of technical professionals facing similar structural challenges, and that **progress in one domain can catalyse change in others**.

Together, these examples show that reducing inertia and improving recognition does not require starting from scratch. Building on existing guidelines, sharing best practices, and aligning local actions with international recommendations can meaningfully improve recognition, support career development, and strengthen the sustainability of core facilities.

Highlight Box 2: Practical tips for core facilities to improve recognition practises identified by survey respondents and GBI Working Group members

- Familiarise yourself with existing institutional guidelines and promote their uptake.
- Initiate authorship and acknowledgement discussions during project kick-off or training sessions.
- Use facility policies or terms & conditions to formalise expectations of recognition
- Provide clear text blocks for acknowledgements.
- Provide regular reminders to your users - via reminder emails, inclusion in your email signatures, notifications in booking systems and on computer login screens or desktop backgrounds, acknowledgement posters.
- Maintain visible records of publications that acknowledge the facility.
- Support users in drafting methods sections, which enables the facility to learn about ongoing manuscripts - and ensure correct details are included for improved methods reporting.
- Monitor talks/presentations, reports, and publications, and address discrepancies where appropriate.
- Provide training for researchers, especially Early Career Researchers, on working with core facilities and applying authorship guidelines.
- Adopt a PID (e.g., ROR IDs) for your facility to standardise facility citation.

⁶ <https://hidden-ref.org/>

⁷ <https://itss.org.uk/tsn/>

⁸ <https://itss.org.uk/>

⁹ <https://www.techniciancommitment.org.uk/>

A Call to Action on recognition

The findings presented in this manuscript demonstrate that inadequate recognition of Imaging Scientists working in core facilities is a global and systemic issue with direct consequences for career development, institutional sustainability, and research quality. Across regions and facility types, recognition consistently emerges as a foundational factor that shapes career progression, funding stability, workforce retention, and the long-term resilience of imaging infrastructures.

Addressing these challenges requires coordinated action across the research ecosystem. Researchers, facility managers, institutional leadership, publishers, funders, and international networks all have a role to play in embedding fair and transparent recognition practices into everyday research workflows. While community-driven tools and initiatives already provide practical pathways forward, their impact ultimately depends on institutional commitment and systemic uptake.

We therefore encourage research institutions to critically review their authorship and acknowledgement practices, ensure that existing guidelines are clearly communicated and implemented, introduce the position of a research integrity office as a neutral mediator in cases of academic integrity challenges, and empower Imaging Scientists to participate meaningfully in discussions around credit for their work. In parallel, publishers and funders should strengthen mechanisms that promote transparent reporting of facility contributions, including consistent acknowledgement practices and the use of persistent identifiers.

More broadly, recognition must be embedded within evaluation frameworks. Hiring, promotion, and performance assessments for Imaging Scientists and other core facility professionals should reflect the full scope of their contributions: **multidisciplinary technical expertise, methodological innovation, training, service provision, data stewardship, and community-building**, rather than relying predominantly on traditional publication metrics alone (11). Aligning evaluation practices with the realities of facility-based science is essential for establishing equitable, attractive, and sustainable career pathways (18,19).

By acting collectively and building on existing momentum, the research community can ensure that Imaging Scientists and all core facility experts - who enable, accelerate, and safeguard scientific discovery, receive appropriate recognition, and that core facilities are fully integrated as valued contributors within the academic research ecosystem.

Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive, global analysis of the structural challenges facing Imaging Scientists working in core facilities, integrating evidence from two complementary international surveys. Together, the findings demonstrate that career progression, recognition, funding stability, training access, and workforce sustainability are deeply interconnected elements of a single ecosystem. Across regions and institutional contexts, the absence of clear career frameworks and consistent recognition

mechanisms emerges as a critical constraint on both individual careers and the long-term viability of imaging infrastructures.

By examining authorship and acknowledgement practices alongside the Top 5 Career Path Challenges, this work highlights recognition as a key mechanism underpinning many of the systemic issues identified. Although no single metric can capture the full impact of Imaging Scientists, visibility in scientific publications remains a key interface between facility-based contributions and institutional and funding evaluation systems. Inconsistent recognition therefore reinforces career-path misalignment and limits the ability of facilities and individuals to demonstrate impact, secure resources, and sustain expertise.

Importantly, the findings also show that progress is already underway. Community-driven initiatives, shared guidelines, and emerging institutional and national frameworks demonstrate that recognition practices can be improved when responsibility is shared and solutions are grounded in everyday research practice. Imaging Scientists are part of a broader global community of technical specialists, and the imaging field is well positioned to continue to contribute leadership and transferable models for recognition reform. We hope to revisit this data in the years to come to benchmark progress in the evolution of this field.

Building on earlier international recommendations, this manuscript provides an evidence base to support coordinated, system-level change and first suggestions to the different types of stakeholders how they can each contribute to this change (see Box 1). Strengthening recognition practices is not only a matter of fairness; it enhances **research quality, reproducibility, data integrity, and institutional resilience**. Ensuring sustainable career pathways for Imaging Scientists and securing the future of imaging core facilities are inseparable goals. Addressing them requires recognition to be embedded at the core of research ecosystems so that sustainability, excellence and innovation are not undermined.

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Supplemental Material 1 – Survey questions of both international surveys

TOP5 - Challenges regarding Career in Imaging Core facilities Survey Questions

Question 1: I work in an Imaging Core Facility - Identify as per Figure 1 (Venn)*

Question 2: At my institution, my current position is formally known as:

Question 3: I have held another position in a core facility in the past, formally known as:

Question 4: Name

Question 5: Institution/ Core Facility/Infrastructure

Question 6: City *

Question 7: Country *

Question 8: Top 1 - Free answer text *

Question 9: Top 2 - Free answer text *

Question 10: Top 3 - Free answer text *

Question 11: Top 4 - Free answer text

Question 12: Top5 - Free answer text

Question 13: Please pick the category that best fits your TOP1 challenge *

- FUNDING- lack of financial and sustainability strategy or not enough funds security
- VALUE- Lack of understanding of the Value & Impact of Imaging Core Facility Scientists
- MISMATCH - between the classic "academic" career path and the "other" more service-oriented path
- TRAINING- Not enough dedicated training offers or opportunities
- TALENT - Challenges with recruiting and retaining expertise
- OTHER - none of the above

Question 14: Please pick the category that best fits your TOP2 challenge (choices as above) *

Question 15: Please pick the category that best fits your TOP3 challenge (choices as above) *

Question 16: Please pick the category that best fits your TOP4 challenge (choices as above)

Question 17: Please pick the category that best fits your TOP5 challenge (choices as above)

Question 18: OTHER- if there is a section you think we should include, please let us know!

Question 19: If you could pick TWO of the listed strategies, which would you prioritise?

* Indicates obligatory questions

Authorship and Acknowledgement of Imaging Core Facility contributions in publications survey questions

All questions in this survey were optional

Section 1:

Question 1: Email

Section 2:

Question 2: About you and your facility (Optional)

Question 3: Do you work in an imaging core facility:

- Yes
- No
- I don't work in an imaging core facility, but I fulfil a core facility staff equivalent role in my department/institution (e.g. support and train other researchers in using imaging equipment, quality management of shared use imaging instruments)

Question 4: In what country are you based?

Question 5: What is your gender identity?

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary/Third gender
- Prefer not to say

Question 6: What is your primary role within the imaging core facility?

- Facility Manager
- Facility Administrator
- Technical Specialist
- Image Analyst
- User support
- Other

Question 7: What is the team size of your Imaging Facility (incl. all staff)?

- 1 -2
- 2-5
- 5-10
- 10-20
- >20
- n/a

Question 8: What kind of imaging services does your facility offer?

- Electron Microscopy
- Light Microscopy
- Intravital Imaging
- Preclinical Imaging
- Clinical Imaging

- Image Analysis
- Other

Question 9: What is your job title?

Question 10: Have you held previous roles in the core facility? If yes, please list them under the "other" option.

- Yes
- No
- Other

Question 11: What is the equivalent of the salary for your current role in the core facility?

- Roughly equivalent to PhD student
- Roughly equivalent to postdoc researchers
- Roughly equivalent to PI/Professor
- Roughly equivalent to Dean/Head of Department
- Other

Question 12: Which best describes your position?

- Academic track (post-doc, lecturer, professor etc.)
- Technical staff track (research technician, RTP, administrative staff etc.)
- Other

Question 13: What aspects of research do you contribute to in your role in the imaging core facility?
[Select all that apply]

- Methodology Development
- Data analysis/interpretation
- Experimental design
- Manuscript preparation
- Literature review
- Grant writing
- Collaboration facilitation
- Teaching or mentoring
- Other

Section 3: Recognition of your facility in publications

Question 14: Within your facility team, how frequently are team members given authorships of publications for their contributions to these publications?

- Rate 1 (Never) to 10 (Always)

Question 15: Are there institutional policies or guidelines regarding authorship recognition for core facility staff at your institution?

- Yes
- Yes, but they are not clearly defined
- No, there are no such policies
- Not sure

Question 16: If you would be willing to share your institutional or facility guidelines, please upload them here (Upload document if available).

Question 17: If there are institutional policies, how often are they taken into account in reality?

- Rate 1 (Never) to 10 (Always)

Question 18: Are there any proactive steps taken to promote recognition of core facility contributions in publications?

- Yes - driven by the core facility
- Yes - driven by the department/institution
- Yes - by other initiatives
- No
- Other

Question 19: If you answered yes in the previous question, please briefly describe the proactive steps being taken (Free text answer)

Question 20: How frequently are team members from your core facility team acknowledged in publications in these different forms?

- First/primary Author
- Co-author
- Last Author
- Acknowledged in the acknowledgments section
- Not acknowledged

Ranked as:

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always
- Not applicable

Question 21: How satisfied are you with the current recognition of core facility imaging scientists in authorship?

- Rate Not Satisfied (1) to Very Satisfied (10)

Section 4: Barriers to authorship and acknowledgement

Question 22: Are there any barriers preventing imaging scientists in your core facility from being recognized in authorship? Select all that apply.

- Lack of awareness of their contributions
- Institutional culture
- Lack of leadership support
- Lack of advocacy for recognition
- Lack of clear policy from publishers/journals
- Other:

Question 23: Have you observed any gender disparities in authorship recognition for core facility imaging scientists?

- Yes
- No

- Not Sure

Question 24: Have you observed disparities in acknowledgements for imaging facility staff with and without a PhD title?

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure

Question 25: Have you observed facility managers receiving authorships while the staff who contributed to the project have not received authorship?

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure

Question 26: How do you think authorship recognition for imaging scientists could be improved?

- Clearer institutional policies
- Increasing awareness of core facility contributions with researchers
- Increasing awareness of core facility contributions with institutional leadership
- Inclusion of authorship recognition policy in training for students
- Advocacy for recognition
- Requirements/guidelines from publishers
- Broad adoption of the Credit system
- Other

Section 5: Your Individual Experience

Question 27: How often have you in the past received authorship recognition that were appropriate for your contributions?

- Rate 1 (For none of the projects I contributed to) to 10 (For all of the projects I contributed to)

Question 28: If you are not offered authorship by the facility users, have you advocated for authorship for yourself and your facility colleagues?

- Yes
- No
- Occasionally

Question 29: If you do not generally advocate for authorship for yourself and your facility colleagues, why not? (Free Text Answer)

Question 30: Have you ever experienced disagreements or conflicts regarding authorship credit for your contributions?

- Yes
- No

Question 31: How do you typically communicate your contributions to a research project to ensure appropriate authorship recognition? (Free Text Answer)

Question 32: Do you feel that lack of authorship attribution and acknowledgements impact any of the following?

- Job evaluation

- Promotion
- Ability to secure funding
- Future Career Prospects
- Ability to attract and retain staff
- Ability to attract external academic users
- Ability to attract industry users

Ranked by:

- Not at all
- Somewhat
- To a large extent
- Fully

Section 6: Open Feedback

Question 33: Do you have any suggestions or recommendations for improving the process of authorship recognition for contributions like yours?

Supplemental Material 2

Detailed breakdown for countries included in geographical representations in Figures 2, 5 and 10.

Africa - Cameroon, Egypt, Kenya, Nigeria, Rwanda, South Africa, Uganda

Asia - Indonesia, India, Indonesia, Israel, Japan, Malaysia, Pakistan, Philippines, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, Taiwan, Thailand, Turkey

Europe - Albania, Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom

Oceania - Australia, New Zealand

North America - Antigua & Barbuda, US, Canada, Mexico

South America - Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Guatemala, Paraguay, Uruguay